

The Application of Deep Learning in Electroencephalography signal Analysis

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Abstract

This article aims to use the processing of electroencephalogram (EEG) signals of images generated by the brain. This study expands an existing solution by exploring the gains of adapting classifier parameters to the user. In the first step, we developed a deep learning model that extracts features from raw EEG signals and predicts the image among 40 possible classes from the ImageNet dataset. The main goal of this paper is to adapt this model to new users to create a unique model based on the minimum number of new users.

Keywords: Deep Learning, LSTM, EEG signal, ImageNet, Machine Learning, Electroencephalography.

Introduction

This study aims to improve the relationship between man and machine in a cerebral approach. Brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) store, analyze, and interpret the signals generated by the brain [1, 2]. Electroencephalogram is the most common method to read brain signals. Before machine learning methods became common, it was not easy to investigate these signals, but with deep learning, this complexity has become much less. Deep learning is a method that employs artificial neural networks with a very large number (deep) of layers. The objective here is to show the salient features of signal extraction. The use of these signals may be more in the future, but due to the complexity of calculations, it is currently being investigated in research and industrial dimensions. For example, Facebook has allocated one of its research fields to investigating EEG signals. Mark Zuckerberg says: "We are trying to decode words that you can type from your brain on the phone five times faster than today." Elon Musk is also trying to improve people's lifestyles with the help of BCI by producing a brain chip implant. BCI can help disabled people to communicate better or control and move affected limbs [2]. Moreover, BCI can combine virtual and actual reality to control the game directly with the brain without using hands. This method is even helpful in improving some diseases, such as mental diseases [3, 4]. In this paper, an attempt has been made to analyze the brain EEG signal during detecting the observed object in a photograph [4, 5, 6].

With the help of deep learning in multi-layer neural networks and a more advanced state with convolutional neural networks, accurate answers to classification questions can be provided. Here LSTM model is used, which is the best option for sequence queries. Here, the EEG signal is analyzed with the help of deep learning. All these analyses will be performed in the Keras & TensorFlow environment. EEG signals have been used for image analysis with the help of machine learning and deep learning methods. For example, in [7, 8, 9], it has been tried to detect the object in the images from the EEG signal. In [10, 11], the classification of car images has been performed. In [12], it is tried to generate an SVM model to create a personalized model. Other researchers have also utilized machine learning models, although they have not directly used raw EEG data. In [13, 14], P300 signals are used, which is a method to analyze decision-making.

In [15], a system was designed to control a robot's movements by the brain. Furthermore, the EEG signal analysis makes it possible to find treatment methods for brain diseases such as epilepsy [16]. Even in the investigation of airline frequencies, frequency analysis can be done with the help of extracting various features [18, 20]. EEG signals can also detect emotions such as anger, happiness [17], and feelings caused by listening to a type of music [21]. In [22], conventional machine learning methods explore decision-making. Each type of data requires a different deep-learning method [19]. The convolutional neural network is also employed in examining EEG signals. For example, it analyzes the resulting information like an image in [24]. In [23], an image is created with the values of each sensor electrode on the skull. In [25], it processes EEG signals directly. The advantage of deep learning here is that it extracts features without changing the frequency. The LSTM architecture is an excellent way to check the sequence of signals. In [27], two model classifications and evaluation methods are presented. This model is based on ImageNet with 40 classes. In this method, the LSTM model has 130 neurons.

Methodology

The dataset is always significant step in deep learning. There are plenty of different datasets for deep learning with different types of data like EEGlearn, kaggle, OPen MRI which could be found in BNCI Horizons. Spaminato data [26] is selected, which works with 10-20 electrodes or a 128-channel brain cap. This test analyzes a person's vision with images from ImageNet with 40

classes. The pause time for playing each image was 2 seconds. Like figure 1, a neuron layer with a bias has been utilized to facilitate the results

Figure (1) Dense layer architecture

The reason for using the RNN network and LSTM model is the time sequence in EEG signals. As shown in Figure 2, LSTMs are a better choice because of their memory and gate-like shape mechanisms that reduce the problem of bursting and loss of some gradients. First, the sigmoid function's task is to decide whether it is necessary to forget the previous step.

Figure (2) LSTM behavior example

Then, new calculations of the sigmoid value are performed based on the TNAH function, which finally obtains the final output of LSTM. Here the cross-entropy categorization is selected [27, 28]. Adam and RMSprop were utilized for the optimizer. One hot encoding method has been used to select a single class, and the activation function is SOFTMAX. According to the EEG signal with 128 electrodes, the length of the input vector is [128,200] with 20-30 epochs and 200 samples per patch [29, 30]. Figures 3 describe the model well. Due to the 500-millisecond window size, only 200 samples are selected.

Figure (3) Universal model initial and final architecture

This choice is removed in the first 50 samples due to the possibility of overlap with the images. Hence, the difference between the two approaches will be between 50-250 milliseconds and 250-450 milliseconds, according to the amount of variance.

Results and Discussion

According to the graphs of accuracy and loss in figures 4, several peaks can be obtained by storing the model's weight in the most prominent peak. On the other hand, the probability distribution between different classes is shown in Figure 5. The normal distribution is a simple way to determine how the error is distributed between classes, whether they are all specific to the same class or not. Figure 5 shows that proper classification is performed and the confusion matrix which shows that the classification is implemented well.

Figure (4) Accuracy and loss in final model

Figure (6) Classes distribution: Real vs predicted Samples at left and Probability distribution at right. (classes vs. samples) and Confusion Matrix of samples

This figure is instrumental in finding the accuracy and distribution of the output model. This model, whose comparison results can be seen with [31, 4], can be evaluated between 40 classes. An offset of 250 out of 50 gives better results. On the other hand, with the help of RMSprop instead of Adam, the results will be better. Considering that in this paper, four topics with 40 image classes and two topics with 30 image classes are used, and ten classes have been rejected due to incomplete recording, noises are produced. So the average results of ft3-6 are similar. In Table 2, the maximum accuracy is 90%. This amount reaches 92% for the second category subjects.

Table 2 - Results of Universal model 30 classes. Offset 50 vs 250 and Adam vs Rmsprop

Model	Classes	Train Acc	Val Acc	Test Acc
UNIVERSAL-Adam o50	30	76.55 %	73.80 %	72.00 %
UNIVERSAL-Rmsprop o50	30	87.6 %	88.54 %	87.98 %
UNIVERSAL-Adam o250	30	77.72 %	77.46 %	74.04 %
UNIVERSAL-Rmsprop o250	30	89.50 %	91.06 %	89.80 %

In order to achieve a more comprehensive model, we use the p-value to have a better-personalized model. With the help of the p-value, it is possible to reject or accept the results due to the null hypothesis. This value should be less than $p=0.004$.

Conclusions

The main goal of this paper is to process EEG signals with deep learning techniques. BCI has diverse applications, and studies are expanding. In this research, the critical achievement was an increase in accuracy compared to previous works, with an accuracy of 89% using images of 40 classes of the ImageNet dataset.

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